

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 25, No. 1

Dear Readers,

Welcome to the first regular issue in 2019 which presents novel research in three high quality papers. Allow me to emphasize that this would not be possible without the valuable work and feedback of the editorial board and the financial support of the consortium. We are continuously looking for experienced and motivated experts to extend our editorial board: if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board. Please get also in touch with me if your university is interested in joining the consortium and further support the journal, in particular institutions from North and South America might further complement our team.

In a collaboration between researchers of Poland and Germany, Rafal Kozik, Michal Choras and Jörg Keller propose a new approach to cyber attack detection on the basis of the practical application of the efficient lifelong learning cybersecurity system B-ELLA which is a new balanced extension of the Efficient Lifelong Learning (ELLA) framework. Gerardo Maturro, Florencia Raschetti and Carina Fontán from Uruguay report the results of a systematic mapping study to identify existing research on soft skills in software engineering and to determine what soft skills are considered relevant to the practice of software engineering where 30 main categories of soft skills based on 44 papers were introduced. Marcos Yukio Siraichi, Caio Henrique Segawa Tonetti, and Anderson Faustino da Silva from Brazil introduce in their research an auto-tuning system for compiler optimizations that uses hot functions to guide the process of exploring and employs machine learning technique combined with an iterative compilation technique to find an effective compiler optimization sequence.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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